

Status of the Ecotourism Industry in Selected Towns of the Province of Cebu

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ABSTRACT

Ecotourism is a vital aspect of tourism development in the Philippines, especially in rural areas where natural beauty attracts tourists and provides opportunities for local engagement. Despite its potential to alleviate poverty, many ecotourism sites remain untapped or underdeveloped. This study examined ecotourism activities in selected municipalities of Southern Cebu in 2022, aiming to propose action plans for Local Government Units (LGUs) to enhance ecotourism development.

A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection. Quantitative data were gathered through adapted survey questionnaires from Adeleke (2015) and Sheldiasheva (2019), covering residents' and visitors' profiles, ecotourism activities, sources of information, preferences, participation, and impact assessments. Qualitative data were collected via interviews using a guide adapted from Gorica et al. (2016), exploring site designations, challenges, and strategies from six local tourism officers or focal persons.

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The study involved three groups: 150 resident respondents, 210 visitor respondents, and six key informants. Results showed that most residents were males aged 36 and above, residing in the locality for over 41 years, while visitors were mainly young adults (26–29), college-educated females from within Cebu, traveling with family or friends. Key ecotourism activities included trekking, swimming, hiking, mountaineering, wildlife watching, and community interaction. Main sources of information were friends, internet, brochures, and media.

Residents strongly agreed on the importance of maintaining ecotourism areas through policies and community engagement. Visitors affirmed the environmental, social, economic, and infrastructural benefits of ecotourism. Thematic analysis revealed key challenges: lack of sustainable promotion, poor infrastructure, and sustainability issues. In response, strategies included multifaceted marketing, diversifying activities, and transforming sites toward sustainability.

The study concludes that Southern Cebu's ecotourism offers significant development potential and benefits, reinforcing the need for strategic planning and stronger LGU involvement.

Keywords: Tourism development, ecotourism, mixed method, Cebu Province, Philippines

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Tourism is the most popular industry for developing the local economy in the world. Apart from the economy's development, tourism can also bring many advantages to local government and residents. (Siriwardana, 2019). Also, tourism is a unique industry, which, instead of delivering goods and services to a consumer, transports consumers to a product where the production of goods coincides with their consumption (Wilson & Ypeij, 2012).

Ecotourism is a new kind of tourism that encourages responsible travel to natural places, focusing on protecting the environment, helping local communities stay healthy, and educating visitors on conservation and protection efforts. It is a holistic approach to tourism that tries to minimize the adverse effects of travel while maximizing the benefits it can provide to the environment (Toronto School of Management Team [TsoM], 2019).

The concept of ecotourism has been the most dramatic outcome of the environmental movements and insurgency that showcased the sustainability limitations of mass tourism. From a humble beginning in the 1980s, in which ecotourism was perceived mainly as visitation to natural areas for enjoyment and education (Ceballos-Lascurain, 1996), the meaning of the concept had by the turn of the 21st century broadened to

incorporate environmental conservation, economic development, social inclusion, cultural preservation, human rights and ethical issues (e.g., Donohoe & Needham, 2006; Fennell, 2008). However, after an initial period when ecotourism was welcomed as a positive alternative to mass tourism, there is some ambivalence as to its true meaning or purpose today.

Moreover, ecotourism can boost economic growth and social welfare while protecting the environment (Libosada Jr., 2009; Parks et al., 2009; Kiss, 2004; O'Neill, 2001). Eshun and Tonto (2014) added that ecotourism helps develop community-based natural resource management and alternative livelihoods. It creates jobs and income to boost economic development. This increases economic activity, reduces economic risk, and creates opportunities for local ecotourism businesses (Kiper, 2013).

Due to the challenges faced by the drivers and stakeholders of the ecotourism industry in the country, particularly in Cebu Province, this investigation aims to determine the ecotourism activities in the identified eco-tourist destinations in the Province of Cebu year 2022 with the end view of crafting action plans for each of the Local Government Units (LGUs).

Theoretical / Conceptual Framework of the Study

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This research is anchored on the following theories: The Theory of Environmentally-Responsible Behavior by Hines et al. (1987), the Value-Belief-Norm Theory of Environmentalism by Stern (1999), and the Environmental Citizenship Model by Hungerford and Volk (1990). Also, this is supported by the following legal bases: Executive Order No. 111, series 1999, “Establishing the Guidelines for Ecotourism Development in the Philippines,” DOT, DA, DILG, and DENR Joint Memorandum Circular No. 01, series 2020, “Rules and Regulations Governing the Conduct of Marine Wildlife Tourism Interactions in the Philippines,” and Republic Act No. 9593, “The Tourism Act of 2009”.

The Theory of Environmentally Responsible Behavior (ERB) was developed by Hines, Hungerford, and Tomera (1987). The model contends that having the intention to act is a significant factor affecting ERB (Elisha, 2022; Okafor et al., 2022). This model indicates the following variables: intention to act, locus of control (an internalized sense of personal control over the events in one’s own life), attitudes, sense of personal responsibility, and knowledge suggested whether a person would adopt a behavior or not. This model considers the significant variables that play a part in the individual process of ERB adoption. The internal control center significantly impacts the intention of acting, which substantially determines an individual’s ERB. This model also highlights a

relationship between the control center, the attitudes of individuals, and their intention to act. The authors asserted that the control center directly affects an individual’s attitudes, which can lead to an improved intention to act and behavior. Thus, the theory concentrates more on existing interactions between parameters that influence a person’s behavior than on the singular impact of a single variable (Akintunde et al., 2017).

Figure 1.

Study

The

Theories of the

motivation to

behave, locus of influence (an internalized sense of personal control over one's own life's events), attitudes, sense of personal responsibility, and knowledge are all predictors of a person's propensity to engage in a behavior, according to the Model of Responsible Environmental Behavior (Akintunde, 2017; Ernst et al., 2017; Gifford & Nilsson, 2014).

- Profile of the tourist, residents and Local Tourism Officers/Focal persons
- Residents' ecotourism activities
- Eco-tourist visitors' sources of information regarding the ecotourism destinations & preference for ecotourism activities
- Local residents' willingness to participate in ecotourism perception on ecotourism
- Ecotourism visitors' assessment on the impact of ecotourism
- Challenges encountered by the Local Tourism Officers/focal of ecotourism destinations
- How Local Tourism Officers/focal participants address the identified challenges in ecotourism

- Descriptive-survey research design
- Data Gathering
- Data Analysis
- Presentation of Data
- Interpretation of Data

Proposed
Action Plan

INPUT

PROCESS

OUTPUT

Figure 2. *Schematic Diagram of the Study*

Through its supervisory function, the DILG shall monitor and oversee Local Government Units through memoranda, guidelines, and the like in managing and patrolling tourism activities and developments in marine wildlife interaction sites to ensure the enforcement of all these rules and regulations. The lead agencies shall involve scientific or academic institutions and conservation groups in all the significant phases of implementation of this Circular. Moreover, the lead agencies shall consult their Regional Offices, if any, on the availability of funds and workforce to regularly monitor tourism wildlife interaction sites.

Statement of the Problem

This research determined the ecotourism activities in the identified ecotourism destination sites in the Province of Cebu, Year 2022. The results will be used as the bases in formulating proposed action plans for each of the Local Government Units [LGUs].

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub-questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

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1.1. local residents

1.1.1 age;

1.1.2 gender; and

1.1.3 years of stay in the locality;

1.2. ecotourism visitors

1.2.1 age;

1.2.2 gender;

1.2.3 highest educational attainment;

1.2.4 type of tourist;

1.2.5 residence; and

1.2.6 travel description;

1.3. Local Tourism Officers/Focal persons

1.3.1 designation; and

1.3.2. name of the ecotourism site?

2. Based on the perceptions of the local resident respondents, what is their ecotourism activities?

3. Based on the perceptions of the ecotourism visitors, what is their:

3.1. sources of information regarding the ecotourism destination sites; and

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- 3.2 preference for ecotourism activities?
4. Based on the perceptions of the local residents, what is their level of:
 - 4.1. willingness to participate in ecotourism; and
 - 4.2. perception on ecotourism?
5. Based on the perceptions of the ecotourism visitors, what is the level of impact of ecotourism?
6. What are the challenges encountered by the Local Tourism Officers/focal performs of ecotourism destination sites?
7. How did the Local Tourism Officers/focal participants address the identified challenges in ecotourism?
8. Based on the findings, what action plans may be proposed?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlined the research methodology containing the research design, instrumentation, data-gathering procedures, and the statistical treatment of the data obtained.

Research Design

This study used a mixed research method, employing quantitative and qualitative research methods.

The quantitative research design used an adopted survey questionnaire to gather data relating to the respondent's profiles for the residents and visitors, residents' ecotourism activities, sources of information regarding the ecotourism destination sites, visitors' preference for ecotourism activities, residents' willingness to participate in ecotourism activities, and visitors' assessment on the level of impact of ecotourism.

Research Environment

This investigation was conducted in the ecotourism sites in the selected municipalities in Southern Cebu, such as Alcoy, Aloguinsan, Alegria, Argao, Carcar City, and Dalaguete. The following are the areas that were particularly covered.

Bojo River is in the Southwestern part of Cebu. It is situated in Aloguinsan Cebu, a 4th class Municipality. It said that Bojo is a Spanish word that means coastal sailing or

trading, which would make sense once the visitors learn along the cruise that there was once an area near the river mouth where farmers and fishermen would trade their goods way back before the currency was invented. The local authorities and inhabitants manage it.

Sumbria River is one of the few recognized ecotourism sites under the management of the Department of Tourism. It is found in Barangay Taloot, Argao Cebu. It is right beside the pier of Taloot, where passengers from Bohol are coming in.

Mabugnao-Mainit Spring is a very unique ecotourism site. It is the only ecotourism site that has both hot and cold springs. The said site is known not only for its spring but also for its beautiful cave. It is operated by the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office, which caused the local government of Carcar City to be unable to develop the area. The site is 7.6 km away to the west of the mainland, Carcar City.

Osmeña Peak stands at 1,013 meters above sea level. Interestingly, the said tourist destination is known to be owned by the Municipality of Dalaguete. This is due to its access to the area. It is also maintained and managed by the above-mentioned Local Government Unit. However, it is geographically part of the Municipality of Badian.

Research Participants

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In this study, three (3) groups of research participants participated in this investigation. The first (1st) group was the one hundred fifty (150) respondents, consisting of twenty-five (25) residents each from the Municipality of Alegria (n=25), Municipality of Aloguinsan (n=25), Municipality of Alcoy (n=25), Municipality of Argao (n=25), Carcar City (n=25), and Municipality of Dalaguete (n=25) who resided near the ecotourism site. The second (2nd) group was the two hundred ten (210) respondents comprised of thirty-five (35) visitors each from the Municipality of Alegria (n=35), Municipality of Aloguinsan (n=35), Municipality of Alcoy (n=35), Municipality of Argao (n=35), Carcar City (n=35), and Municipality of Dalaguete (n=35). The selection of these two groups of respondents applied a random sampling technique.

Moreover, six (6) research informants were the Local Tourism Officers or focal persons of the ecotourism destination sites. The selection of this group of participants chose purposive sampling techniques.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized three (3) sets of research instruments. The first instrument was an adapted questionnaire from Adeleke (2015). The second instrument was an adapted questionnaire from Sheldiasheva (2019). The third instrument is an Interview Guide adapted from the SEA-Med Project in Albania by Gorica et al. (2016).

The first (1st) set of survey instruments is intended for the residents and consists of three (3) parts. The first (1st) part consists of items about the residents' profiles, including their age and gender and years of stay in the locality. The second (2nd) part of the instrument contains items about the residents' ecotourism activities (multiple responses). The third (3rd) part concerns the local residents' willingness to participate in ecotourism and their perceptions of it. The respondents were instructed to rate the items using the 4-point Likert scale: 4 points for Strongly Agree, 3 points for Agree, 2 points for Disagree, and 1 point for Strongly Disagree.

The second set of survey instruments is intended for ecotourism visitors and comprises three (3) parts. The first (1st) part 1 consisted of items about the ecotourism visitor-respondents' profile, age and gender, highest educational attainment, type of tourist, residence, and travel description. The second (2nd) part contains items relating to ecotourism activities, sources of information regarding the ecotourism destination sites, and the visitors' preference for ecotourism activities. The third (3rd) part is about the perceptions of the impact of ecotourism. The respondents were instructed to rate the items using the 4-point Likert scale, with the following equivalents: 4 points for Strongly Agree, 3 points for Agree, 2 points for Disagree, and 1 point for Strongly Disagree.

The third (3rd) type of research instrument is the interview guide for the tourism officer or focal person of the ecotourism destination sites, comprising three (3) parts. The first part contains preliminary questions, while the second (second) part gathered the ecotourism activities. The third (3rd) part is about the challenges encountered and the strategies or ways of the local tourism officers/focal participants in addressing the identified challenges in ecotourism.

Data Gathering Procedures

The following procedures are employed in the gathering of data.

Phase 1

The researcher submitted a letter asking permission from the Dean of the Graduate School and Professional Studies of St. Paul University Surigao to conduct the study. When approval and proper recommendation from the Dean were secured, a letter of intent and permission to conduct the study and interview was sent to the Office of the Provincial Tourism Officer of the Province of Cebu.

Phase 2

When approval from the Provincial Tourism Officer was secured, a letter of endorsement was sent to the Local Tourism Officer/Focal of the ecotourism destinations in the Province of Cebu. The researcher handed in the Informed Consent Form [ICF] to

the ecotourism visitors and read its contents regarding their involvement in the study. They were asked about their willingness to participate. To those who signified their affirmative decision, the researcher gave a copy of the survey questionnaire for them to answer, and they were given ample time to accomplish this. Then, the retrieval of the answered survey tool was done after.

Also, the researcher provided a letter of intent to interview the Local Tourism Officers or focal persons of ecotourism destination sites in each of the Municipality of Alegria, Municipality of Aloguinsan, Municipality of Alcoy, Municipality of Argao, Carcar City, and Municipality of Dalaguete. A schedule was set for a personal interview with them, and an in-depth interview was conducted.

An informal orientation was undertaken to explain the objectives of the study to the participants. They were also assured that all the data provided would be treated with utmost confidentiality and that their identities would not be divulged to anyone. The study results were communicated appropriately to all local tourism officers/focal, and no personal information was divulged to anybody. This study was conducted for the betterment of the participants who have full knowledge of ecotourism. Through the study findings, the researcher designed an action plan to improve further the implementation of ecotourism destinations in Cebu Province.

Data Analysis

The following statistical formula is used to analyze the quantitative data:

Frequency, simple percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used on the respondents' profiles.

Frequency count, simple percentage, and rank were used to analyze the data on the residents' profiles and perceptions of ecotourism activities and the ecotourism visitors' sources of information regarding the ecotourism destination sites and their preference for ecotourism activities.

Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data relating to the residents' willingness to participate in ecotourism and the perceptions of the ecotourism visitors on the level of impact of ecotourism.

Thematic analysis was applied in analyzing the narratives from the Local Tourism Officers or focal persons of ecotourism destination sites on the challenges encountered and ways of addressing the identified challenges in ecotourism.

Summarized Data on the Perceptions of Ecotourist Visitors on the Impact of Ecotourism (n = 210)

Indicators	Aggregate Mean	StDev	Interpretation
Ecotourism			
1. Comforts my daily life.	3.63	0.56	Strongly agree
2. Conserving natural resources.	3.57	0.58	Strongly agree

3.	Creates adequate income.	3.54	0.57	Strongly agree
4.	Creates employment for local residents.	3.66	0.60	Strongly agree
5.	Helps economic development.	3.67	0.56	Strongly agree
6.	Helps visitors support resource conservation.	3.62	0.56	Strongly agree
7.	Improves my knowledge about the environment.	3.56	0.60	Strongly agree
8.	Improves regional construction on roads and bridges.	3.40	0.65	Strongly agree
9.	Improves the quality of life.	3.52	0.62	Strongly agree
10.	Increases environmental awareness.	3.62	0.58	Strongly agree
11.	Increases the sense of unity among local residents.	3.56	0.61	Strongly agree
12.	Links visitors and local residents with good interactions.	3.54	0.62	Strongly agree
13.	Motivates me better towards the environment.	3.64	0.56	Strongly agree
14.	Promotes social welfare.	3.60	0.57	Strongly agree
15.	Provides adequate interpretative facilities.	3.53	0.58	Strongly agree
16.	Provides cultural exchange opportunities.	3.47	0.61	Strongly agree
17.	Provides excellent environmental educational experiences.	3.60	0.55	Strongly agree
18.	Provides interaction between people and their cultures.	3.65	0.52	Strongly agree
19.	Provides satisfaction to visitors on recreational quality.	3.59	0.63	Strongly agree
20.	Site has provided a unique sense of appreciation.	3.60	0.57	Strongly agree
Overall Aggregate Mean		3.58	0.59	Strongly agree

Legend: Range: 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree 151

Ecotourism helps in community development by providing an alternate source of livelihood to the local community, which is more sustainable. It aims to conserve resources, especially biological diversity, and maintain sustainable use of resources, bringing the ecological experience to travelers, conserving the ecological environment, and gaining economic benefit. However, achieving the aims of ecotourism depends on

whether they are environmentally and ecologically sustainable and economically applicable.

THEMATIC CATEGORIES OF THE KEY PARTICIPANTS’ RESPONSES

Common Themes Emanating from the Responses of Key Participants

This section presents the themes pertaining the challenges or issues and concerns of the Municipal Tourism Officers or focal persons.

Figure 3. *Challenges or Issues and Concerns of the Municipal Tourism Officers or Focal Persons*

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, findings, conclusion, and recommendations.

Summary

Over the years, tourism has played a significant role in boosting the economy of the country, including the developing nations, like the Philippines. One of the important concept of tourism development in the Philippines, ecotourism, where the uniqueness and beauty of the natural environment attracts multitude of tourist to come and visit the countryside to engage with nature and leisure activities. However, the potential of ecotourism to alleviate one of the problems in the rural area, which poverty has not been fully addressed because there were lots of potential sites that were untapped and undiscovered by either the government or the private sector.

This study used a mixed research method, employing quantitative and qualitative research methods. The quantitative research design used an adopted survey questionnaire to gather data relating to the respondent's profiles for the residents and visitors, residents' ecotourism activities, sources of information regarding the ecotourism destination sites, visitors' preference for ecotourism activities, residents' willingness to participate in ecotourism activities, and visitors' assessment on the level of impact of ecotourism. Moreover, the qualitative methods applied the exploratory research design with the

adopted interview guide to gather data about the designation and name of the ecotourism site, challenges encountered by the local tourism officers or focal of ecotourism destinations, and strategies or ways of the local tourism officers/focal participants in addressing the identified challenges in ecotourism. This investigation was conducted in the ecotourism sites in the selected municipalities in Southern Cebu, such as Alcoy, Aloguinsan, Alegria, Argao, Carcar City, and Dalaguete. In this study, three (3) groups of research participants participated in this investigation. The first (1st) group consisted of one hundred fifty (150) respondents, while the second (2nd) group consisted of two hundred ten (210) respondents. Six (6) research informants were the Local Tourism Officers or focal persons of the ecotourism destination sites. The researcher utilized three (3) sets of research instruments. The first instrument was an adapted questionnaire from Adeleke (2015). The second instrument was an adapted questionnaire from Sheldiasheva (2019). The third instrument is an Interview Guide adapted from the SEA-Med Project in Albania by Gorica et al. (2016). For data analysis, frequency, simple percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used on the respondents' profiles; frequency count, simple percentage, and rank were used to analyze the data on the residents' profiles and perceptions of ecotourism activities and the ecotourism visitors' sources of information regarding the ecotourism destination sites and their preference for ecotourism activities.

Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data relating to the residents' willingness to participate in ecotourism and the perceptions of the ecotourism visitors on the level of impact of ecotourism. Thematic analysis was applied in analyzing the narratives from the Local Tourism Officers or focal persons of ecotourism destination sites on the challenges encountered and ways of addressing the identified challenges in ecotourism.

Findings

The following are the significant findings of this study:

1. More local residents were 36 years old and above and had stayed in the locality for 41 years and above, while most were males. More ecotourism visitors were 26 to 29 years old and college graduates, while the majority were females, local tourists, residing within the Province of Cebu and traveling with family and friends. The research informants were designated as Tourism Officers or Focal Persons of their respective municipalities, Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Officers (MENRO), and Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Planning Officers (PENRO).

2. The top ecotourism activities among the residents in Southern Cebu were watching the natural environment, trekking, hiking, mountaineering, swimming, interacting with the local people, and river cruising.

3. The top sources of information concerning the ecotourism destinations in Southern Cebu were friends or relatives, the internet, brochures or guidebooks, television, and radio, while the top ecotourism activities preferred by the visitor respondents in Southern Cebu were trekking, hiking, and mountaineering, swimming, watching the natural environment, interacting with the local people, and maintaining the undisturbed environment.

4. The resident respondents *strongly agreed* that they believed that the operation of the ecotourism site in many areas of Southern Cebu entails maintaining the site as a protected area through a law or government policy with close community engagement.

5. The ecotourism visitor respondents *strongly agreed* that the existence of ecotourism destination sites in the abovementioned municipalities in Southern Cebu brought environmental, social, economic, and infrastructural benefits to the people and visitors.

6. The themes developed in the challenges encountered by the local tourism officers/focal ecotourism destinations are the Dearth of Sustainable Promotional Program for Ecotourism Sites, Gaps in Tourism Infrastructure Hampered Tourism Activities, and Developing Sustainable Tourism. The themes emanated from the strategies or ways of addressing the identified challenges in ecotourism are Multi-faced Tourism Marketing

Strategies, Diversifying Ecotourism Activities, and Transforming Tourist Sites Towards Sustainable Activity. The ecotourism activities offered by the sites are Swimming and Cruising, Trekking and Camping, and Wildlife Watching.

Conclusions

Ecotourism development in the Province of Cebu, particularly the southern corridor, with the influx of visitors who were interested in engaging and enjoying the magnificent and distinct beauty of nature like the Nug-as forest, Mt. Lanaya, Bojo River, Sumbria River, Mabugnao-Mainit Spring, and Osmeña Peak wherein the local community and the visitors enjoyed viewing the natural environment, trekking, hiking, mountaineering, swimming, interacting with the local people, and river cruising.

Moreover, with the proliferation of the Internet and social media sites, visitors can quickly obtain information about the ecotourism sites in Southern Cebu. Hence, the local people consider the existence of ecotourism sites in their locality to play a vital role in providing social, economic, and environmental benefits. While the people enjoyed their endowed resources from nature, they were engaged in environmentally directed practices to sustain the ecotourism operations so that the people could obtain a sustainable source of livelihood and improve their standard of living. However, it cannot be denied that the government implementers of policies to regulate the operations of the site faced a

shortage of promotional efforts to attract more tourists due to the lack of social overhead capital. Thereby, there is a need to have well-defined marketing efforts to boost leisure and sports activities.

Recommendations

Based on the crucial revelations from the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

1. That Local Government Units in Alegria, Alcoy, Aloguinsan, Argao, Carcar City, and Dalaguete will adopt the proposed action plan to provide framework in the development and promotion of ecotourism sites in their respective locality;
2. The local government policymakers will propose ordinances to adopt proposed action plan and to appropriate budget to provide social overhead capital and other infrastructural needs; and
3. That the Department of Environment and Natural Resources [DENR] will be heighten the implementation policies that protects the natural environment.
4. That future researchers will undertake the following research topics:
 - 4.1. lived experiences of the tour guides in Southern Cebu;

- 4.2. feasibility of government and community partnership in green practices at ecotourism site; and
- 4.3. exploring the potential ecotourism sites in Cebu province.

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